

Review of state of the art of use of models and satellite EO observations for water resources modelling

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List of Acronyms

AET	Actual Evapotranspiration
ALOS	Advanced Land Observing Satellite
ARS	Agricultural Research Service
AMSR-E	Advanced Microwave Scanning Radiometer-EOS
ASCAT	Advanced Scaterometer
ASTER DEM	Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer Digital Elevation Model
C3S	Copernicus Climate Change Service
CAMS	Copernicus Atmospheric Monitoring Service
CDR	Climate Data Record
CEMS	Copernicus Emergency Management Service
CGLS	Copernicus Global Land Service
CHIRPS	Rainfall Estimates from Rain Gauge and Satellite Observations
CLC	Corine Land Cover
CLMS	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service
CMORPH	Climate Prediction Center morphing method
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DHI	Danish Hydraulic Institute
EAWAG	Swiss Federal Institute of Aquatic Science
EDO	Earth Dynamics Observatory
EFAS	European Flood Awareness System
EMS	Emergency management Services
EO	Earth Observation
ERA-5	ERA5 provides hourly estimates of a large number of atmospheric, land and oceanic climate variables.
ESA CCI	European Space Agency Climate Change Initiative
EU	European Union
ET	Evapotranspiration
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
GDO	Global Drought Observation
GIS	Geographical information System
GLDAS	Global Land Data Assimilation System
GLOFAS	Global Flood awareness System
GMTED 2010	Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data
GPM	Global Precipitation Measurement
GPM IMERG	Integrated Multi satellite retrieval for global precipitation measurement
GLEAM	Global Livestock Environmental Assessment Model
GUI	Grafical User Interface
HBV	Hydrologiska Byråns Vattenbalansavdelning
HEC-HMS	Hydrological Engineering Center - Hydrological Modeling System

HEC-RAS	Hydrological Engineering Center -River Analysis System
HRU	Hydrological response unit
LAI	Leaf Area index
LFI	Low Flow Index
LISFLOOD-FP	Hydrological model -Flood prediction
LISFLOOD	CEMS hydrological model
LSWT	Lake Surface Water Temperature
LU/LC	Land Use Land Cover
MERRA-2	Modern Era Retrospective Analysis for Research and applications (version 2)
Mike HYDRO	DHI water allocation tool
Mike SHE	DHI suite of hydrological and hydraulic modelling tools
MMU	Minimum mapping unit
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer Sensor
MODSIM	Model simulation tool for water allocation
MSWEP	Multi Source Weighted Ensemble Precipitation
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space administration
NCEP CFSR	National Center for Environmental prediction Climate Forecast System Reanalysis
NDVI	Normalized difference vegetation index
PERSIANN	Precipitation Estimation from Remotely Sensed Information using Artificial Neural Networks
PERSIANN CCS	PERSIANN Cloud Classification System
RIBASIM	River Basin Management Tool
Rrs	Remote Sensing Reflectance
RS	Remote Sensing
SA	Sensitivity assessment
SEBAL	Surface Energy Balance Algorithm for Land
SEBS-ETa	Surface Energy Balance
SEI	Stockholm Environment Institute
SMAP	Soil Moisture Active/Passive
SMOS	Soil Moisture Ocean Salinity
STRM DEM	Shuttle Radar Topography Mission DEM
SWAT	Soil and Water Assessment Tool
TMPA	TRMM Multi-satellite Precipitation Analysis
TRMM	Tropical rainfall measuring mission
USDA-NRCS	United States
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe
USDA	United States Department of Agriculture
USGS	United States Geological Survey
VIC	Variable Infiltration capacity

WEAP	Water Evaluation And Planning
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The Horizon2020 project Water scenarios For Copernicus Exploitation (Water-ForCE) will develop a Roadmap for Copernicus Inland Water Services. The Roadmap will assess the current state of water related services provided by six existing Copernicus Services and will provide an optimal way forward for satisfying different user and stakeholder communities.

The current report provides an overview of the available modelling tools for modelling water quantity in general, and the use of Remote Sensing data (RS) for modelling, such that the model outcomes are useful to decision makers. The aim of the report to assess the availability of Copernicus services for water quantity modelling and give recommendations where in the hydrological processes modelling they can be used. Conclusions formulates recommendations for the Water-ForCE final roadmap.

1. Introduction

1.1 Water-ForCE

Water resources vary with the changes in climate, population demand partly due to population growth and their patterns for using water in different activities (Winemiller et al., 2016). The inland freshwater resource determines the economic growth and environmental status. (Muhammed et al., 2019). Nowadays, apart from providing direct data on the Earth Observation, Remote Sensing (RS) technologies support research in different domains such as environment, agriculture, land management, forestry, etc. In water domain field experts use RS data to obtain the parameters linked to both water quality (Papathanasopoulou et al., 2019) and water quantity. In particular experts using RS target various objectives: operating with RS data for modelling (hydrological and hydraulic models); comparing RS data to modelling outputs for calibration and/or validation; using RS data as input to empirical predictions for extreme events, such as floods and droughts for decision making, etc. These methodologies can strongly contribute to the alarm systems and disaster management (Sarker et al., 2020). Other applications of RS technology are combining spatial datasets on land use from RS and spatially-explicit hydrological modelling to quantify the impact on water-based ecosystem services (Netzer et al., 2019).

Remote Sensing methodologies have seen major improvements over the last decade, but their uptake is still limited, owing to a lack of skills within sectors that could benefit from Remote Sensing capability, limited confidence and overall lack of concerted effort to support their validation and integration. In the EU the Copernicus programme was initiated to fill spatial and temporal gaps in availability of environmental data for management and decision making.

In this context the **Horizon 2020** project **Water-ForCE** (Water scenarios for Copernicus Exploitation) is developing a Roadmap to better integrate the entire water cycle within the [Copernicus services](#), thereby addressing needs and requirements from the user community, the current disconnection between Remote Sensing / in-situ observations and upgrade of the modelling algorithms.

The Roadmap will contain:

- Analysis of user communities' landscape
- Analysis on how Copernicus water services can support policy development and monitoring of their implementation
- Gap analysis of the Copernicus water-related service portfolio
- Identification of future higher-level biogeochemical products
- Technical requirements for future Copernicus sensors to improve the water-related service portfolio
- Proposal for organising in situ measurement networks to validate Copernicus Remote Sensing and modelling products and to provide complementary data not collected by Remote Sensing
- Proposal on how to define relationships between Core Services and Downstream services
- Recommendation on the evolution of a water service (via the creation of a new service, or the improvement of water services under current Copernicus services, or through a better integration of water-related products)

The Water-ForCE project is coordinated by the University of Tartu (Estonia) with 20 participating organisations from all over Europe. It connects experts in water quality and quantity, in policy, research, engineering and service sectors. The project is divided into eight work packages (WP), each of them focusing on a specific problem and/or target of the Copernicus services. The project started on 1st of January 2021 with a duration of three years.

This report is part of Work Package 3 (WP3) “Water quantity”, of which overall objective is to provide insight on the Copernicus products (floods, drought, surface water extent, soil moisture, ice, ...) and services supporting water management and modelling. The report looks at the current state in modelling water quantity, and where RS is available to be used as input or as model parameters.

1.2 Purpose of this document

The current report provides the current state of the art in modelling water quantity in general, and the use of Remote Sensing data (RS) for modelling it, such that model outcomes are useful to decision makers. The aim of the report is to look at availability of RS services to provide data for water quantity modelling in general, as found in literature. The report gives special attention to availability of Copernicus services, in order to better formulate recommendations for the Water-ForCE final roadmap.

1.3 Content of the Report

This document starts with an introduction presenting the scope of WaterForCE project, followed by Section 2 on modelling principle, and model structures. As modelling water quantity requires specific vocabulary a set of definitions for the notions on modelling used in the report is provided. A special section is dedicated in section 2 to uncertainty evaluation and sensitivity analysis. As this deliverable aims at addressing how water quantity is modelled and which RS data and services are used for modelling, the uncertainty introduced by RS data inputs is in the scope of deliverable D5.2 of Water ForCE, where it is presented in high detail. Therefore here only model uncertainties are addressed.

Section 3 provides an overview of the most used tools for water quantity modelling, along with those tools used for water allocation. As there are a variety of tools developed by different schools, Section 3 ends with a list of other available tools. Links to where information about these tools can be found is provided the subsection on other tools. A literature review, of the last 5 years publications on the use of RS as data inputs for the modelled case studies with the presented tools is shown in this section. Section 4 of the report shows the available Copernicus services that could be used as data inputs for water quantity modelling, as they have been identified and presented in deliverables 3.2 and 5.2, are summarised. The report ends with Section 5 Conclusions, where recommendations for the Water-ForCE final roadmap are provided.

2. Inland water quantity modelling

This chapter provides an overview of water quantity modelling approaches and their use to quantify inland water availability. Such models serve a wide range of purposes in water resources management, predicting water quantity, or quality, including ecosystem services in time and space.

Most models require large amounts of data which may not be available. Remote sensing technologies are a part of the solution, as they offer spatially distributed information. After identifying the generic structure of a hydrological model, an overview of where RS can contribute with data is detailed, based on literature search, availability of remote sensing services in general, and Copernicus in particular, and based on the outcomes of previous deliverables in WaterForCE, in particular D1.4, D1.6; D3.2, D3.3, D5.1; and D5.2. The deliverable ends with a detailed overview on how uncertainty and sensitivity analysis for hydrological model prediction is done.

2.1. Definitions

For the clarity of the deliverable this section makes an inventory of definitions for the terms related to hydrological models and modelling, as they will be further addressed.

(i) Model - a collective term for a representation of the essential aspects of a system, with knowledge of that system being represented in a form that can be used. The definition most used for it is that a model is “a simplification of reality over some time period or spatial extent, intended to promote understanding of the real system” (Bellinger, 2006)

- (ii) System is a part of reality (isolated from the rest). It consists of entities represented through interactions (processes) having limited relations with the reality outside the system (e.g. the terrestrial system; the hydrological system, etc)
- (iii) Modelling implies the construction of a model, or use of a model.
- (iv) Simulation refers to the use of the model to mimic the studied system on a computer.
- (v) Calibration is the process of estimating model parameter values to enable a hydrologic model to match observations
- (vi) Validation is the process of comparing model results with observations that were not used during calibration
- (vii) Data assimilation is a set of statistical techniques that incorporate observation data into hydrological models, with the goal of optimizing output results (and possibly parameters). The results of a data assimilation framework needs to be superior to that from the model or observations alone
- (v) Catchment or river basin is the geographical (scale) system used to manage water quantity. In such a system, precipitations will contribute to the flow, usually generated in a single outlet. Catchment is a suitable unit for studying rainfall-to-runoff processes. At the catchment scale, water can be considered a resource (for water supply, irrigation, etc), or a hazard (e.g. flood, droughts, etc).

2.2. Scope of modelling, model types and structure

Water resources are important for any country to fulfil its basic citizen needs and economic growth. Mathematical models are used in order to adequately determine water resources availability. Sorooshian et al. (2008) states the well-known "a model is a simplified representation of real world system", with best model the one which give results close to reality with the use of least parameters and model complexity. However, regardless of simplicity, most models require large amounts of data, both for model building and model usage.

In order to understand the problem solved by a model, they are classified depending on the level of mathematics involved in developing them and on how simulation is done (Lane and Nichols, 1993). A system analytical approach is used to develop a model. First the processes and how the system works need to be well understood. After a model is built, the responses can be analysed through the outputs. Moreover, knowing the mathematical description of the processes described by a model, a modeller will not only know the type of output to be expected, but also the amount of information required to build the model. Model classification helps users to select the appropriate model for a particular problem, taking into account the solving need and the data availability (Popescu, 2014). Models determining water quantity are referred to as hydrological models. Though some of the hydraulic/hydrodynamic models are also used to determine water volumes on a reduced area, in this report water quantity, as determined by hydrological models is addressed.

2.2.1. Water quantity modelling

At the catchment scale, whether water is a resource or a risk, one needs to estimate the volumes and temporal distributions of water in that system. Any catchment has a stream where water from the catchment is conveyed. Streamflow is usually measured, however, its estimation through modelling is required for better management and adaptation measures testing. The main aim of water quantity estimation can be achieved through the two previously mentioned objectives.

Water availability in catchment and streams is determined with hydrological models. When there is a need to determine the flood extent, hydraulic/hydrodynamic models are used. Hydrologic and hydraulic processes are interdependent, however distinctly different. Hydrology refers to quantification of

flows that are produced by precipitation (rain, snow, etc) addressing the entire hydrologic cycle. It looks at the quantity of water in a catchment, the rate of surface runoff, and the timing of its arrival at a point of interest (outlet). Hydraulics focusses on the movement of water (velocities, water depths) in streams analysing how water moves from one point to the next. Therefore, hydraulics looks just to a reduced part of the hydrological cycle. Methodologically, hydrology is more descriptive whereas hydraulics is more detailed.

There are several levels of classification of water quantity models (Rhoda and Rhoda, 1999; Singh, 1995), depending on the description of:

- Processes described (water quality, water allocation, reservoir operation, flood management, etc) (Figure 1)
- Mathematical representation of the solution to the problem (Figure 1)
- Time and space problem dimension (lumped conceptual, one dimensional, two dimensional and three dimensional) (Figure 2).

Figure 1. Model Classification based on mathematical representation of the physical system (source: Popescu, 2014)

Figure 2. Models classification based on problem scale (source: Popescu, 2014)

From the solution point of view models are dynamic or static, or they are finite and continuous. A model is dynamic if the state variable is time dependent, and it is static otherwise. The finite and continuous classification refers to the space variables of it. Hence, if the state variables do not depend on the space variables, it is finite, otherwise it is continuous. Usually finite dynamic models represent the

processes by ordinary differential equations; while continuous dynamic models use partial differential equations.

Structurally models are grouped into three main categories:

- 1) Physically based (or "White box") models, which try to account for all processes, and storages. They use partial differential equations governing various physical processes and equations of continuity for surface and soil water flows (Chiew et al., 1993). Deterministic models qualify as white box models
- 2) Data driven (or "Black box") models, which use inputs (rainfall) to transform them into outputs (runoff) with no representation of the processes involved in the transformation. Only the input and the output have physical meaning. Time series analyses fall into this category (Chiew et al., 1993). Stochastic models are considered black box models.
- 3) "Grey box", or "Conceptual" models that represent a partial understanding of processes, with limited possibilities for modelling changes.

Physically based (process based) models can be lumped or distributed, depending on the space representation. Lumped conceptual models are based on the concept of exchanges between global storage entities, i.e. one compartment for surface water, another one for aquifer storage, etc). These models satisfy principles such as the continuity principle, but do not embed a complete description of the driving forces, which govern the system to be modelled (e.g. rainfall-runoff model, reservoir model, etc). Lumped models are often used as catchment and environmental models.

Distributed physically based models use a description of the physical phenomenon which govern the behaviour of water in the system under study. The

principles that are applied are mass conservation and additional laws describing the driving forces.

Data driven models seek just for a correlation between input and output data, without trying to detail/analyse phenomena (e.g. linear regression, unit hydrograph). These models do need a lot of prior knowledge and data observations of the system under study.

Table 1 below gives an overview of the characteristics of the three model types presented: physically based, data driven and lumped/conceptual.

Table 1. Characteristics of models

Element	Physically based models	Data driven models	Conceptual model
Physics of the phenomena	Based on the Physics ("white box")	Data based or metric ("black box")	Parametric ("grey box")
Mathematical representations	Based on distribution. Evaluation of parameters describing physical characteristics	Statistical relations. Derive value from available time series	Based on modelling of reservoirs. Include semi empirical equations with a physical basis
Input data about physical system description	Require data about initial state of model and morphology of catchment	Little consideration of features and processes of system	Parameters are derived from data and calibration
Model complexity and required experience	Complex model. Require expertise and computation capability	High predictive power, low explanatory depth	Simple and can be easily implemented in computer code
Other remarks		Cannot be transferred to other catchments	Require large hydrological and meteorological data
Example tools currently used	MikeSHE SWAT	ANN	HBV TOPMODEL
Validity	Wide range of situations	Valid within the boundary of the given domain of computation	Calibration involves curve fitting make difficult physical interpretation

2.2.2. Model structure

Water modelling process has two components: model building, and model usage. (Figure 3). Model building starts by defining the model setup (input data, schematization and parameters), followed by calibration and validation of measured discharged values. Calibration and validation can be performed for simulation and forecasting models. Model usage entails running simulations by using different input data or introducing designed measures for better flood management (e.g. different land use); or forecasts can be made by using forecasted discharge values. In a simulation setting, model parameters are assumed to be constant in time while, in a forecasting setting the parameters, inputs or states (discharges) can be updated while the model is in use, using data assimilation.

Figure 3. Hydrological models building and use

Model set-up is dependent on the schematization of the processes in the hydrological cycle (motion, loss and recharge of the earth water). The main identified processes of the hydrological cycle are: precipitation, interception, evaporation/evapotranspiration, infiltration, percolation, run-off (surface water

and groundwater), storage (surface and groundwater), and water use and demand. At any point in space, all these processes are a in a different stage, i.e flow (transport), storage (short or long- term) or solid or liquid (including gas state). Depending on the model type, physically based or data driven, the interactions and connections between these components are differently represented in the model structure, i.e either as full representation of the physical interactions through equations, or as functions in the nodes of the data driven model (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Hydrological models' structure: a) Physically based models; b) Data driven models. I-Input, O-output, F- description of the processes, either as differential equations, or as relations in nodes.

Any hydrological model consists of a set of hydrological parameters describing the system (catchment) properties, and algorithms describing the physical processes. There are many ways to define these component interactions.

Estimating input and parameters to be used in models is important as they will contribute to model output, which will support selection of good strategies for water resources management. Acquiring the necessary data for model input and parameters can still be expensive, particularly for rapidly changing systems that

require frequent model updates. When there is lack of data, remote sensing technologies are a part of the solution, as they offer spatially distributed information. However, their availability may be limited, also in terms of space and time, and their uncertainties often are not quantifiable (Grimaldi et al., 2016; Li et al., 2017).

The choice of using a particular model or build a modelling approach depend on the objectives of the study, the available data and also on the user experience. An overview of existing models and the use of remote sensing data for setting up such models, as found in literature, is presented in next section of the report.

2.3. Evaluating uncertainty of hydrological models

A key consideration when using hydrological models is the issue of uncertainty, particularly when several components produce a complex integrated output.

Hydrological models are developed to understand process, test hypothesis, and support decision-making. The main aim of the models is to find solutions of mathematical equations describing the processes, which are empirical and/or complex differential equations. These equations are solved over different space and time scales, i.e they are lumped, semi-distributed, or fully distributed models in space. A second layer of complexity is brought by the extent to which variables and processes are coupled. Although modelling has progressed extensively in the last 15 years in the way the different processes and complexities are accounted for, they still are simplifications of the hydrological processes because of limited data availability, imprecise measurements, and representation of processes that are not yet fully understood. All of these introduce uncertainty, which needs to be quantified.

Two important concepts are related to uncertainty:

- Uncertainty analysis (UA) through which the uncertainty in model outputs are quantified. All these are due to the level of uncertainty in the model set-up
- Sensitivity assessment (SA) is used to investigate how uncertainties in a model or its inputs affect the outputs, and which combinations of model input and parameters are most important in determining the outputs.. As such the most critical can be addressed in more detail.

The sources of uncertainty in hydrological modeling are mentioned by many researchers, as highlighted by Liu and Gupta (2007), and have led to a variety of

methods to estimate and quantify uncertainty starting from early 1992 (Vrugt and Sadegh, 2013).

There are six different sources of uncertainty: parameters, forcing, initial state, model structure, output, and new states. Hydrological modelling, however, requires decisions that will influence uncertainty evaluation (Clark et al., 2015). Except in extremely data rich environments, simple modelling approaches with highly uncertain prediction confidence intervals are often considered superior to complex approaches with highly uncertain inputs and process descriptions (Hrachowitz et al., 2014).

The key elements of a systematic framework for determining uncertainty are:

- uncertainty characterization—which entails assigning small and joint distributions to model inputs that are uncertain
- uncertainty propagation—which involves translating the uncertainty in model inputs into the corresponding uncertainty in model outputs
- uncertainty importance—which determines the key drivers of output uncertainty.

Analyzing uncertainty requires methodological approaches that are separate of the model development. However, uncertainty analysis (UA) is very useful to hydrological models because it is identifying the limitations of the model and helps improving it, including improving its structure. Moreover, UA can further support data collection set-up.

2.3.1. Uncertainty analysis

The sources of uncertainty of a hydrological model are: parameters, model structure, calibration (observation) and input data (Tegegne, 2019).

Moges et al (2020), made a review of uncertainty sources and methods for determining the propagation of uncertainty in the outputs. The main sources of uncertainty and their causes are presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Main sources of uncertainties in a hydrological model (Source: Moges et al, 2020)

The main framework for determining the propagation of uncertainties through a hydrological model are represented in Figure 6

Figure 6. Uncertainty propagation

There are six broad classes of methods to perform UA, as follows:

- Monte Carlo sampling – applied to all four sources of uncertainty in a hydrological model

- response surface-based schemes including polynomial chaos expansion and machine learning – applied to analyse parameter uncertainty – applied to model structure
- multi-modeling approaches – applied to parameter and model structure
- Bayesian statistics – applied to all four types of sources of uncertainty
- multi-objective analysis – applied to parameter uncertainty
- least square-based inverse modelling – applied to parameter uncertainty.

Detail description of these methods, with web pages where extensive theoretical approaches are given, along with downloadable codes is given in table Table 2

Table 2. Summary of uncertainty analysis methods, sources of uncertainty, and webpage source (adapted from Moges et al, 2020)

No.	UA Method	Uncertainty source	Base method	Webpage for download
1	GLUE	parameter/input/ Model structure	MonteCarlo	www.uncertain-future.org.uk/?page_id=131
2	FUSE	Model structure	Monte Carlo	//github.com/cvitolo/fuse
3	Multi-objective	parameter	Multi-objective optimization	//borgmoea.org/ //faculty.sites.uci.edu/jasper/software/ //moeaframework.org/index.html
4	Machine learning	predictive uncertainty	Machine learning	//scikit-learn.org/stable/
5	PEST/UCODE	Parameter/ predictive uncertainty	Least square methods	(a) www.pesthomepage.org/ or (b) //igwmc.mines.edu/ucode-2/
6	Polynomial chaos expansion	Predictive/ parameter uncertainty	Polynomial chaos	(a) www.uqlab.com/feature (b) //muq.mit.edu/ (c) //pypi.org/project/UQToolbox/ (d) //github.com/jonathf/chaospy
7	Ensemble averaging	Model structure	Multi-models	
8	BMA	Model structure	Multi-models and	

			Bayesian statistics	
9	HME	Model structure	Multi-models and Bayesian statistics	//faculty.sites.uci.edu/jasper/software
10	DREAM	parameter/input/	Bayesian statistics	
11	BATEA	parameter/input/ model structure	Bayesian statistics	

Each method presented above has its own advantages and limitations, and there is no one method good for all parameter uncertainty. The variety of techniques gain attention in the last 15 -20 years and have been applied widely. In contrast, model structure uncertainty is very little addressed. More work in this area will help source attribution and interpretation of predictive uncertainty. It is in particular important to use uncertainty propagation in integrated hydrological models.

An important domain where UA has a lot of applicability is the modelling of ungauged catchments. Given that most watersheds across the world are ungauged, future research in this direction is very important, especially when RS data is used as input.

2.3.2. Sensitivity analysis

A sensitivity analysis (SA) to determine the possible values of the parameters of a model and their qualitative and quantitative variations in the output of the model, should be an integral part of any hydrological modelling study (Saltelli et al.2000). Sensitivity analysis of parameters of a hydrologic model entails to give each parameter values in a given range, with small amount of change, one at a time. Based on these changes the corresponding change in the model output are determined. Sensitivity coefficients are computed as the change in output divided

by the change in input, reflecting the slope of the input–output relationship at the reference point.

The functional relationship between the output and the input can be linear or not. In case it is linear over the entire range of input values, information regarding the relative sensitivities of input parameters can be inferred.

If sensitivity of outputs to particular inputs is low, it may be left out in overall uncertainty analysis.

Louks and van Beek (2017) show the relationship between model input parameter uncertainty and model output. This relationship is plotted in Figure 7. Although the UA and SA concepts are similar, and similar methods can be used to perform sensitivity and uncertainty analysis, their purpose is different. Sensitivity analysis is an important tool for model calibration.

Figure 7. Schematic diagram showing the relationship between model input parameters uncertainty and sensitivity to model output (source: Louks and van Beek (2017))

Critical examination of the relations between model inputs and outputs, as defined by Louks and van Beek (2017) is essential because it can help to identify any errors in model structure and definition; can provide guidance for reduction of model parameterization; and can analyze the information content of available observations (Castaings et al. 2007).

3. Water resources models

Water resources models presented in this section are divided in two separate types: hydrological and water allocation models.

A hydrological model is defined by a set of equations that estimate the water quantity (runoff) as a function of various parameters used for describing the hydrological processes in the catchment under consideration.

Water allocation refers to the quantity, quality and timing of water resources between and within different sectors and for different uses (UNECE). All water allocation models are based on a hydrological evaluation of runoff in the catchment under study, and uses the same balance equation for the water quantity as the hydrological models. However, they introduce consumption by stakeholders, that is not a physical process and requires many times prioritisation, hence the need for a separate section presenting them.

3.1. Hydrological models

Water resources models are variate, looking at the relationship of water with the environment within each phase of the hydrologic cycle. The hydrologic cycle as defined in Figure 5 (USGS) is global in nature, however the local response to frequent meteorological events are important at local scales as a response to local conditions. This led in the past decades to the need to study hydrological systems, with support of models, due to the various changes such as rapid urbanisation, deforestation, land cover change, irrigation, etc.

Figure 8. Conceptualization of the hydrologic cycle showing relevant fluxes and storages (source: public domain from USGS)

Figure 5 is the newest diagram of the water cycle, issued by USGS. Its novelty is that in addition to natural processes like ocean evaporation, precipitation over land, and runoff, the diagram features grazing, urban runoff, domestic and industrial water use, and other human activities. Each label in the chart comes from data tracking the significant paths and pools of water worldwide.

Hydrological models investigate different hydrologic phenomena of the hydrological cycle in order to find how previous mentioned variations affect the behaviour of the system. Several hydrological models are available to be used to determine the impact of climate and soil properties on hydrology and water resources. Each model has its own unique characteristics, however as mentioned in section 2 of this report all models use inputs such as rainfall, air temperature, soil characteristics, topography, vegetation, hydrogeology and other physical parameters. The hydrological models can be applied in complex and large basins, as well as small catchments.

The most used hydrological models nowadays are briefly described below.

3.1.1. LISFLOOD

LISFLOOD-FP model started to be developed in 1999 by University of Bristol and the EU Joint Research Centre (Bates and De Roo 2000), as a hydraulic model to estimate flood inundation on river reaches, and consisted of a one-dimensional kinematic wave approximation for channel flow and a two-dimensional diffusion wave representation of floodplain flow. The hydrodynamic model was tested on several river reaches, one of which is a 35-km of the River Meuse in the Netherlands. Since 1999, it has evolved into LISFLOOD, a spatially distributed water resources model, freely available for download at <https://ec-jrc.github.io/lisflood-model/> (last accessed on 16 December 2022). It is important to mention that LISFLOOD-FP and LISFLOOD are different (although complementary) models. In this section only the hydrological modelling version, i.e LISFLOOD is detailed.

LISFLOOD is a GIS-based hydrological rainfall-runoff-routing model that is capable of simulating the hydrological processes at catchment scale, applicable to large and transnational basins. It can address flood forecasting, effects of river regulation measures, land-use change and climate change. As LISFLOOD is a grid-based, it was applied to basins with grid cells as little as 100 metres (for medium-sized catchments); up to 5000 metres for modelling of the whole of Europe; and 0.1° (around 11 km) and 0.5° (around 55 km) for modelling at the global scale.

LISFLOOD can address long-term water balance using daily or sub-daily time steps, and particular flood events at less than an hour or hourly time step intervals. The main result of LISFLOOD is river discharge, however other outputs can be printed on request, such as soil moisture; all written in grids or as time series at user-defined points or areas. LISFLOOD has no graphical user interface, it uses a python wrapper through which the user inputs data.

The current most prominent application of LISFLOOD is within the European Flood Awareness System (EFAS), and the Global Flood Awareness System (GLOFAS) (Alfieri et al., 2020). Both EFAS and GLOFAS are operated under the

Copernicus Emergency Management System (EMS). All input data are Copernicus available data and services.

3.1.2. SWAT

The Soil Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) model is the successor of “the Simulator for Water Resources in Rural Basins” model (SWRRB). Development of SWAT model started in 1990s at the United States Department of Agriculture (USDA) Agricultural Research Service (ARS) (Srinivasin et al,1998). SWAT is a free software in continuous development, available to download from <https://swat.tamu.edu/>. There are several versions of SWAT available, with the latest available SWAT 2012 and SWAT+ currently available. It is a complex physically based model developed for the prediction of the long-term impact of rural and agricultural management practices on water availability; but also on sediment and water quality. Moreover the model can also be used to analyse the impacts of climate change. The pollution considered for the water quality component of SWAT, has its source from agricultural chemical yields in large, complex catchments, where land use and management conditions are varying (Griensven et al, 2006).

SWAT is efficient in performing long term simulations. The model divides the entire catchment into subcatchments, which are further divided into hydrologic response units (HRU), based on their land use, vegetation and soil characteristics. The model requires as input daily rainfall data, maximum and minimum air temperature, solar radiation, relative air humidity and wind speed; as well spatial soil and land use layers. Penman Monteith, Priestly- Taylor and Hargreaves methods are used for the estimation of evapotranspiration. The model uses the water balance equation in the form of (Eq 1):

$$SW_t = SW_o + \sum_{i=1}^t (R_v - Q_s - W_{seepage} - ET - Q_{GW}) \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where SW_t is the humidity of soil, SW_o is base humidity, R_v is rainfall volume in mm water, Q_s is the surface runoff, $W_{seepage}$ is seepage of water from soil to

underlying layers, ET is evapotranspiration, Qgw is ground water runoff and t is time in days.

The graphical user interface (GUI) for SWAT is generated by ArcSWAT, which is a GIS interface that makes available a geodatabase that stores geographic, numeric, input data (as text files), as well as the results of a SWAT model run (Olivera et al., 2006; Winchell et al., 2007). The version of SWAT running on the open source QGIS, called SWAT+, and provides the QSWAT interface.

The Swiss Institute of aquatic science and technology (EAWAG) has developed a tool for calibrating SWAT and evaluating parameter uncertainty of an instantiated model. A similar toolbox is available for SWAT+, available at <https://swat.tamu.edu/software/plus/> (EAWAG, 2015)

Remote sensing has been used as data input for SWAT, as detailed in Table 2 below.

Table 3. Use of RS data for input in SWAT models

Sr. No.	Purpose	Article	Remote sensed product
1	Impact of land use change on hydrology	Hachemaoui et al., 2022	ASTER DEM; Landsat Satellite images to derive the land use maps
2	Multi-objective calibration	Rane and Jayaraj, 2022	STRM DEM; FAO soil data; Landsat images to derive the Land use map; AET from MODIS; LAI from MODIS
3	Multi-objective multi-variable calibration	Alemayehu et al., 2022	DEM from USGS; Landcover from Africover; Soil type from World Harmonized Soil database; ET from GLDAS
4	Role of Actual ET in calibration	Bennour et al., 2022	ET from ETMonitor, GLEAM, SSEBop, and WaPOR; Digital Soil Map of the World; STRM DEM; Rainfall data from CHIRPS
5	Climate change and hydrological droughts simulations	Chen et al., 2022	Soil water content data of GLDAS
6	Groundwater recharge simulation	Dekongmen et al., 2022	STRM DEM; Landsat images to derive the Land use map
7	Representation of forests in hydrological models	Haas et al., 2022	MODIS-derived leaf area index; MODIS ET

8	Hydrological simulations	Junqueira et al., 2022	Satellite-based rainfall (TMPA and IMERG); ALOS PALSAR DEM
9	Evaluation of precipitation datasets	Khan et al., 2022	Rainfall datasets (TRMM, Climate Forecast System Reanalysis); STRM DEM; Globeland30 by National Geomatics Center of China; Soil data from Harmonized World Soil Database
10	Soil moisture data assimilation into hydrological model	Le et al., 2022	SMAP soil moisture product; GPM IMERG Precipitation; NCEP CFSR V2 Air Temperature
Data from Copernicus			
11	Agricultural land use and crop management	Nkwasa et al., 2022	Leaf Index data from Copernicus Global Land Service (GLS); ET from WaPOR (Water Productivity through Open access of Remotely sensed derived data);
12	Soil erosion	Alitane et al., 2022	Sentinel 2 images for Land use; ASTER DEM

3.1.3. HEC- HMS

The Hydrologic Modeling System (HMS), developed by the Hydrologic Engineering Center (HEC) of the U.S. Army Corps of Engineering Center, is one of the most popular rainfall-runoff simulation tools worldwide, due to its free availability and wide applicability. It is available for download at <https://www.hec.usace.army.mil/software/hec-hms/>

A model built using HEC-HMS can simulate hydrologic processes in a catchment using two types of events: event-based or continuous simulation. Different mechanisms can be selected to perform the simulation; each selection requiring different data inputs, corresponding to the specific set-up of the model.

The HEC-HMS is easy to use due to its completely integrated work environment including a database, data entry utilities, computation engine, and results

reporting tools. It comes with a GUI that allows easy navigation between the different inputs and outputs of the HEC-HMS model (Figure 6).

Figure 9. The GUI of HEC-HMS showing its components. (source: public domain HEC)

Remote sensing was used as data input for HEC-HMS models, as detailed in Table 3 below.

Table 4. Use of RS data for setting up HEC-HMS models

Sr. No.	Purpose	Article	Remote sensed product
1	Soil erosion and sediment transportation	Almasalmeh et al., 2022	Landsat 8 image for vegetation cover; ASTER DEM
2	Corrected satellite-based precipitation for improved hydrological simulations	Asadollah et al., 2022	Satellite-based rainfall (TRMM)
3	Hydrological simulations	Daide et al., 2022	ASTER DEM; Landuse map derived from supervised classification of satellite images ASTER.
4	Relationship between hydrological behaviour and morphometrical features	Khalifa et al., 2022	STRM DEM

5	Hydrological simulations	Mokhtari et al., 2022	Satellite-based rainfall (CHIRPS),
6	Effect of land use change on hydrological simulations	Azizi et al., 2021	Landsat satellite images to derive landuse map; STRM DEM
7	Hydrological simulation use satellite-based rainfall products	Gunathilake et al., 2021	Satellite-based rainfall (PERSIANN, PERSIANN-CCS, PDIR-NOW);
8	Rainfall-runoff modelling	Hamdan et al., 2021	MERRA-2 (Power Data Access Viewer); DEM by USGS
9	Hydrological Impacts of Vegetation Cover Changes	Msaddek et al., 2021	ASTER DEM; satellite images of Landsat for Land use map
10	Flash flood simulations	Tang et al., 2021	IMERG rainfall product; Harmonized World Soil Database;
Data from Copernicus			
11	Flood modelling	Tegos et al., 2022	Satellite-based rainfall GPM-IMREG, PERSIANN-CCS, ERA5 Land & MERRA land; Sentinel satellite images

Along with HEC-HMS, USACE provides a specific software for river flow analysis, the River Analysis Systems (RAS). Often HEC-HMS is used in conjunction with HEC-RAS, as HEC-HMS will provide boundary conditions to HEC-RAS. HEC-RAS complements HEC-HMS in detailed water resources management. Similarly to HEC-HMS the use of RS data for setting up HEC-RAS models are presented in Table 4

Table 5. Use of RS data for setting up HEC-RAS models

Sr. No.	Purpose	Article	Remote sensed product
1	Hydrodynamic modelling and ecological impact of dam break	Jiang et al., 2022	DEM from Geospatial Data Cloud (China)
2	Flood modelling	Ahmad et al., 2022	Flood extent map from MODIS images; STRM DEM;
3	Flood hazard modelling	Kumar and Patra, 2022	CartoDEM from Cartosat-1 satellite data (India)

4	Flood modelling	Meena and Jha, 2022	STRM DEM
5	Surface roughness assessment for using in hydrodynamic modelling	Papaioannou et al., 2022	Images from UAV flight to derived the Digital surface model and digital terrain model
6	Flood modelling and mitigation	Ali et al., 2021	Rainfall products (IMERG-F, TRMM_3B42RT, GSMaP_NRT); Landuse map from ESA CCI and Landsat images; Soil data from Harmonized World Soil Database.
7	Flood hazard mapping	Hayat et al., 2021	ALOS 12.5 m DEM
8	Flash flood hazard prediction	Ibrahim, 2021	Satellite image of ArcGIS World Imagery to derive the Landuse map; GPM final rainfall data
9	Glacier and hydrodynamic modeling	Juárez et al., 2021	Topographic data by Alos Palsar; Satellite images from Landsat and Planet labs for mapping of glacier
10	Flood monitoring by hydrodynamic modelling	Pertiwi et al., 2021	Inundated area derived from TerraSAR-X/TanDEM-X satellite images
Data from Copernicus			
11	Flash flood simulation	Elkhrachy, 2022	Rainfall data from NASA Prediction of Worldwide Energy Resources (POWER); Digital surface model (ALOS-30); water areas derived from Sentinel-1 images; Landuse derived from Sentinel-2 images
12	Flood inundation modelling	Cotugno et al., 2021	Rainfall dataset (IMERG); Sentinel-S2 for Landuse/landcover
13	Flash flood modelling	Elkhrachy et al., 2021	Sentinel-1 images for flooded areas

3.1.4. Mike SHE

Mike SHE is a fully distributed physically based model developed as of 1990s by Danish Hydraulic Institute (DHI). It is a commercial software used for many case studies worldwide. Currently it is part of the MikeZERO suite of tools of DHI group. The model accounts for various processes of hydrological cycle such as precipitation, evapotranspiration, interception, river flow, saturated ground water flow, unsaturated ground water flow etc. It can simulate surface and ground water movement and their interactions, sediment, nutrient and pesticide transport in the model area and various water quality problems and can be applied for large watersheds (see Table 5). Refsgaard and Storm (1995) have provided the detailed description of the structure and set up of the model. Because it is a fully distributed model it has the disadvantage that it requires extensive amount of data for physical parameters. The GUI includes pre-processing and post processing modules and has various options for displaying results.

The use of RS data for setting up MikeSHE models are presented in Table 5.

Table 6. Use of RS for MikeSHE models

Sr. No.	Purpose	Article	Remote sensed product
1	Spatial performance evaluation of distributed hydrological model	Gaur et al., 2022	STRM DEM; FAO soil map; AET derived from ERA-5 and Modis datasets; Soil moisture from ESA CCI
2	Simulation of hydrological processes	Liu et al., 2016	TRMM rainfall data; Land surface temperature from MODIS
3	Snowmelt runoff modelling	Altaf et al., 2020	Snow covered area from MODIS data; ASTER DEM
4	Soil moisture simulations	Lou et al., 2019	SMAP soil moisture product; MODIS snow cover; MODIS land surface temperature; MODIS Land types; MODIS Vegetation index; MODIS leaf area index; TRMM rainfall; digital soil map from the Harmonized World Soil Database; SRTM DEM
5	Groundwater modelling	Shu et al., 2018	ET derived from global radiation products of

			Fengyun-2C geostationary meteorological satellite (FY-2C) and FY-2C precipitation products
6	Distributed hydrological modelling	Loliyana and Patel, 2018	SRTM DEM; IRS P6 LISS III satellite imagery to derive landuse map
7	Effect of climate change on water resources	Luo et al. 2017	TRMM rainfall data
8	Analysis of spatial patterns of actual evapotranspiration and land surface temperature	Koch et al., 2017	Vegetation from MODIS satellite images
9	Terrestrial water storage changes	Seyoum and Milewski, 2016	DEM from GEOSPATIAL DATA GATEWAY of USDA-NRCS; Landuse from USGS-EROS
10	Land surface energy flux estimation	Guzinski et al., 2015	LAI and NDVI from MODIS images
Data from Copernicus			
11	Sediment analysis	Kanga et al., 2021	Sentinel 2A data for sediment concentration analysis

3.1.5. HBV

The HBV model stands for "Hydrologiska Byrans Vattenavdelning model" was developed by the Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute (SMHI) for cold regions in 1973. It is a semi distributed conceptual model (Bergstrom, 1976) considering a basin divided into sub catchments, which are further divided into different elevation and vegetation zones. It runs on daily and monthly rainfall data, air temperature and evaporation. Because it was developed initially for cold regions it has a component for snow, air temperature data is used for calculating snow accumulation. HBV is freely available and different research groups have developed parallel versions of it. It has been applied successfully to forecast runoff for more than 200 river basins in Sweden and has been successfully applied several other countries to study hydrological processes under climate change, changes of permafrost, and changes of land use.

It does not have a GUI, and it relies on the user experience to work with input files.

The use of RS data for setting up HBV models are presented in Table 6

Table 7. RS data used for HBV models

Sr. No.	Purpose	Article	Remote sensed product
1	Hydrological simulation	Geshnigani et al., 2021	Reference ET from FAO's WaPOR product
2	Impacts of climate variation and regional human activities on streamflow changes	Kazemi et al., 2021	Landsat satellite imagery
3	Flood simulation by satellite-based rainfall products	Zhu et al., 2021	Satellite based rainfall datasets
4	Multi variable calibration	Nesru et al., 2020	satellite-based actual evapotranspiration (SEBS-ETa)
5	Soil moisture data assimilation	Pauwels et al., 2020	the Soil Moisture Ocean Salinity (SMOS) product
6	Multi variable calibration	Demirel et al., 2020	Soil moisture from ESA CCI SM v4.4, AMSR-E, SMAP. Total water storage from GRACE
7	Hydrological model improvement	Huang et al., 2020	Evapotranspiration from MODIS and the Global Land Evaporation Amsterdam Model (GLEAM)
8	Hydrological study in glacierized catchment	Wang et al., 2019	satellite rainfall product (TRMM), DEM (SRTM), Soil distribution map (Harmonized World Soil Database)
9	Hydrological diagnosis	Yacouba et al., 2019	DEMs from STRM and ASTER
10	Impact on flow simulation by the downscaling of rainfall datasets	López et al., 2019	Satellite rainfall product (CMORPH, PERSIANN, TRMM, MSWEP)
Data from Copernicus			
11	Effect of Inclusion of soil moisture in calibration of hydrological model	Kuban et al., 2021	CLC 2006, SoilGrids 1km, ASCAT surface soil moisture dataset

12	Multiple objective calibrations of a conceptual hydrologic model	Tong et al., 2021	CLC 2006, ASCAT soil moisture data, and MODIS snow cover data
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3.2. Water allocation models

Water demand for domestic consumption, energy, and food is expected to rise as a result of demographic changes, economic development, urbanization, and climate change, among other factors.

Water allocation determines who can use shared water resources, for what purposes, in what quantity and of what quality, where and when. As water becomes more and more scarce and competition between different sectors intensifies, water allocation is one of the biggest challenges in water management and protection.

In all water allocation problems there are context specific and interconnected objectives, such as: equitable and reasonable use of shared water resources; environmental protection; climate change adaptation; management of special circumstances, such as droughts and floods; human needs; or benefit-sharing.

The most used models for water allocation are presented as structure, in order to identify their data needs input, and where RS data can contribute to set-up of the model, or to the evaluation of available resources.

3.2.1. Water Evaluation and Planning System (WEAP)

The Water Evaluation and Planning (WEAP) tool, was developed in 1988 and is supported by the Stockholm Environment Institute (SEI, 2016). It is a tool for integrated water resource planning providing a comprehensive, flexible, and user-friendly framework for water and environmental policy analysis.

There are three functionalities available in WEAP:

- Water balance database: WEAP provides a system for maintaining and processing information on water discharges and abstractions,

- Scenario generation tool: simulates water demand, supply, outflow, flow, storage volume, pollution generation, purification and discharge, and water quality,
- Strategy Analysis Tool: WEAP assesses a range of options for water development and management, taking into account the diverse and conflicting uses of water systems.

Based on the three above-mentioned functionalities, WEAP examines alternative water development and management strategies, by applying the basic principle of water balance accounting, to single basins and sub-basins or complex river systems. It can address a wide range of issues, e.g., sectoral demand analyses, water conservation, water rights and allocation priorities, groundwater and streamflow simulations, reservoir operations, hydropower generation, pollution tracking, ecosystem requirements, and project benefit-cost analyses.

The main concept is to represent the system under study with supply and demand elements. Supply is represented as various sources: rivers, creeks, groundwater, and reservoirs. Demand is seen as withdrawal, transmission and wastewater treatment; ecosystem requirements, water requirements by different stakeholders (agriculture, industry, hydropower).

The main Graphical user interface (GUI) of WEAP is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 10. WEAP main GUI (Source: WEAP User manual)

There is a special component on Hydrology. After calculation of scenarios WEAP provides the Results and Overviews view. WEAP does not have the capability to read and analyse satellite images, however input from RS can be used as data input for WEAP.

Remote sensing was noted to be used as data input for WEAP, as detailed in Table 7, where authors, purpose and products used are shown. No Copernicus data was used so far in setting up a WEAP model.

Table 8. Remote sensing products used in WEAP as reported in last 5 years literature

Sr. No.	Purpose	Article	Remote sensed product
1	Monitoring spatio-temporal variation of groundwater level and salinity	Moumane et al., 2021	Landsat satellite images to derive the landcover
2	Water resources management under climatic and human impacts	Tarkeshdouz et al., 2021	MODIS AET and MODIS landcover
3	Vegetation dynamics	Zhang et al., 2021	NDVI and LAI from GIMMS

4	Water demand analysis	Chebet et al., 2019	SRTM DEM; Landsat satellite images to derive land use
5	Water management	Loukas et al., 2015	AET from SEBAL by Landsat satellite images

3.2.2 MODSIM

Since 1979, Colorado State University has developed and maintained the Generalized River Basin Management Decision Support System, called MODSIM. The model allows a wide range of analyses from short-term daily operations requiring hydrologic flow routing to long-term monthly river basin planning and management.

MODSIM can model allocation of water based on defined water rights, storage ownership and economic valuation. An important objective in MODSIM development has been to provide an easy-to-use modelling platform, which led to the development of a sophisticated GUI through which river network is created and creation, as well as easy data import and editing. MODSIM can simulate river groundwater interactions for conjunctive use of surface water and groundwater. Only one paper mentions use of RS data for setting up a MODSIM model, as shown in Table 8

Table 9. Use of RS data in a MODSIM model

Sr. No.	Purpose	Article	Remote sensed product
1	Multi-crop planning and optimization	Fereidoon and Koch, 2018	DEM from NASA; FAO soil map; HadGEM2-ES climate model projections

3.2.3. Mike HYDRO

Mike HYDRO, formerly known as Mike BASIN, is an integrated water resources management software program that allows allocation, management, and planning of water resources at a river basin scale. Mike HYDRO is developed by Danish Hydraulic Institute (DHI group).

Mike HYDRO models represent the system under study using two main modules, the basin module, and the river module. The basin module consists of a network of rivers and nodes that allows the user to allocate, manage, and analyse water resources at a basin scale. The processes represented in a model are: watershed runoff (given as input), river flow processes (with or without routing), ground water (linear reservoir approach, water balances for reservoirs including rainfall/evaporation on lake surface), and water quality of runoff and river flow. The simulation run computes water availability at each node and between nodes, taking into account all defined routing. In Mike HYDRO, river basins can be of any size ranging from small to large scale international river basins. It also allows for the representation of multiple river basin, hence allowing for inter-basins water transfer. Simulation time is continuous and has no limit in terms of length of simulation period.

The main Graphical user interface (GUI) of MikeHYDRO, basin component is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 11. Mike HYDRO, the basin module interface (the demo example of the Mike HYDRO installation)

The river module, a subset of MIKE 11, is a 1D river hydraulics model. Mike HYDRO has been used for reservoir optimization, sediment transport, water quality, and streamflow forecasting.

The main concept in MikeHYDRO is the network model that represents rivers and tributaries by a network of branches and nodes.

Remote sensing was noted to be used as data input for MikeHYDRO, as detailed in Table 9, where authors, purpose and products used are shown. No Copernicus data was used so far in setting up a MikeHYDRO model.

Table 10. Remote sensing products used in Mike Hydro as reported in last 5 years literature

Sr. No.	Purpose	Article	Remote sensed product
1	Discharge simulation	Vijhani et al., 2022	Land use derived from Landsat satellite images; solar radiation, wind speed, and relative humidity for the NASA-POWER; SRTM DEM
2	Water levels assimilation	Schneider et al., 2018	Water level observations from CryoSat-2 satellite data; TRMM rainfall data
3.	Water volumes availability	Nishat and Mahbubur Rahman	Water resources modeling of the Ganges-Brahmaputra-Meghna river basins using satellite remote sensing data

Details on where in the Mike HYDRO model structure data inputs from RS, both general and Copernicus in particular are presented in the next section of the report.

3.3 Other models

The models presented in previous sections are the ones most used, and reported in literature for water quantity and water allocation. However there are a number of other models that are available and for which a lot of documentation on how to be used is available in the public domain. Those that are often used and available for download are:

- a. Water accounting and Water accounting +, is an open source application that offers insight into water availability, water flows and water use within a basin. It is available for download at <https://wateraccounting.un-ihe.org/welcome-water-accounting-plus-0>
- b. VIC (Variable Infiltration Capacity model) is a semi distributed grid based hydrological model which uses both energy and water balance equations. The processes like infiltration, runoff, base flow etc are based on various empirical relations. Surface runoff is generated by infiltration excess runoff (Hortonian flow) and saturation excess runoff (Dunne flow). Development and maintenance of the VIC model is led by the UW Hydro | Computational Hydrology group in the Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering at the University of Washington. More information is available at <https://vic.readthedocs.io/en/master/>
- c. TOPMODEL is a semi distributed conceptual rainfall runoff model that is based on the topographic information related to runoff generation. Its development started in 1997 (Beven and Kirby ,1979). A version of it is available for download [here](#).
- d. RIBASIM (River Basin Planning and Management) is a licenced software distributed by Deltares. It is an integrated approach to the water quantity availability for long-term, sustainable management of environment. It has the capability to allocate water in case of scarce resources at the river basin level. The distribution of it and more information is available at <https://oss.deltares.nl/web/ribasim>

4. Remote sensing data availability for modelling water resources

A literature search on the use of RS data for setting up models using the tools mentioned in section 3 of this report gave a list of 735 papers in Web of Science and Scopus. The review looked at the last 5 years of publications.

The diversity in presented applications and modelling approaches of the water quantity issues, in the selected papers, led to the need to define where RS data is used, as shown in Figure 9, either as input (forcing data); calibration of model parameters, validation of model results, evaluation of model performance or data assimilation.

Figure 12. Use of Remote Sensing / satellite-based data products in hydrological modelling

Inputs and parametrization for hydrological and water allocation model set-up as needed from Copernicus are presented in Table 10. These are inputs and Copernicus data needs are outcomes of the surveys carried out during project time, workshops, meetings with stakeholders, and deliverables 3.2 and 5.2 of Water ForCE project.. Figures depicting these services and available data are available in D3.2, where an overview of all Copernicus available data and services is presented. Moreover, D5.2 contains the list of Copernicus services with their temporal and space resolution. Table 10 presents the overview solely based on what is available in D3.2 and D5.2

Table 11. Copernicus services and data available for hydrological modelling, as defined in D3.2 and D5.4 of WaterForCE

Inputs data needs for model set-up	Available Copernicus services	Details
[1]	[2]	[3]
Precipitation data	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. C3S 2. CEMS 3. CAMS 	There are more than 100 products related to precipitation in Copernicus. The most important ones are detailed in the present report, immediately after this table
Land cover map	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CLMS 2. Corine Land Cover 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Only available from 2015 to 2019 Spatial resolution: 100 meters 2. Only available from 1990 to 2018 Remarks: There are 44 LU/LC classes available at a Minimum Mapping Unit (MMU) of 25 hectares (ha) for areal phenomena and a minimum width of 100 m for linear phenomena
Soil map	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. C3S, 2. CEMS, 3. CLMS 	There are 54 soil-related products identified in the water quantity inventory. The most important ones are detailed in the present report after this table
Digital Elevation Maps	CLMS	All these products are offered for the EEA39 zone and with a spatial resolution of 25m. The most important ones are detailed in the present report after this table
River cross-sections	Not available as such	
Water demand	In case of droughts <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CGLS, 2. C3S, 3. CEMS Global water storage availability <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. CEMS (in the GDO (global scale)) 2. EDO (European scale) 	There are 15 products available for drought and 2 products available for Total Water Storage
Hydraulic structures data	Not available	

Reservoir geometry data	No specific data available	
Water level (in reservoirs)	1. CLMS, 2. C3S	1. There are 2 products available from Land Monitoring Service as vector type, global and near-real time 2. One product is available as point data at daily and 10 days temporal resolution
Stream flow data (Q)/River discharge	1. C3S as:	There are 9 products available for Europe area; Global area (except for Antarctica) Temporal resolution: Daily and monthly Spatial resolution: 5 km The most important ones are detailed in the present report, immediately after this table
River network	1. CLMS –	This is comprised of lakes, large rivers and coastal waters. Temporal scale: 2006-2012. Spatial resolution: Minimum Mapping Unit (MMU): 1 ha Remarks: River Network database is available for 39 countries

For each of the parameters and data presented in Table 4 details on the most important products used for hydrological and water allocation model set-up are:

- a) *For precipitation*: precipitation; rainfall accumulation; accumulated precipitation; accumulated rainfall, convective precipitation; convective rain rate; Liquid precipitation duration fraction; Mean total precipitation rate; monthly precipitation (especially for water allocation models); number of dry spells; standardized precipitation Index; mean annual precipitation; total precipitation.
- b) *For soil moisture*: Soil moisture, Initial soil moisture; soil depth; percolation; soil moisture content; soil water content; surface soil moisture; soil moisture Index; volumetric wilting point.
- c) *For Digital elevation model*: elevation, slope, aspect and hillshade.
- d) *For Drought parameters*: combined drought indicators, aridity, water and wetness, low flow index (LFI)

- e) *For River flow*: minimum river discharge; river discharge, maximum river discharge, river discharge in the last 24 hours, river discharge in the last 6 hours.
- f) *For Water levels*: water levels in lakes, water levels in rivers, water surface height

5. Conclusions and recommendations

In general, hydrological models are the standard tools used for understanding and exploring what is happening in hydrological processes. Models can be applied from small catchments to large ones and eventually as global models, depending on how they have been defined during development. Each model has its own unique characteristics and consequently they are valid for specific applications. Some models use the physics of the underlying hydrological processes and are distributed in space and time, requiring large amounts of data that are not always available from in-situ monitoring stations or surveys. RS data and services should be used. However, while using RS data it is important to understand the limitations since they are not only retrieved as raw data, but also using algorithms which are not without uncertainties themselves.

There are a lot of RS services and data, not all used in modelling. Deliverable 5.4 of Water ForCe shows which RS services in general, and in particular which ones of Copernicus are used by modellers to support decision making and policy development. This deliverable gives an overview of what Copernicus services and data are available for modelling in Table 10.

The models are used for the modelling of both gauged and ungauged catchments, are used for flood forecasting, water resources management, erosion and sedimentation, nutrient and pesticide circulation, land use and climate change etc. Each model has various drawbacks like lack of user friendliness, large data requirements, absence of clear statements of their limitations etc. In order to overcome the stated drawbacks, it is necessary that models include rapid advances in remote sensing technologies, such as data regarding reservoir water levels.

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- D3.3 Review document and recommendation on the use of Copernicus products and services supporting water management
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